

Integrating HPC Centers with JENA Computing Infrastructures: Key Findings and Recommendations

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Introduction

The conclusions of the Joint ECFA-NuPECC-APPEC (JENA) Computing Workshop, held in Bologna on June 12–14, 2023¹, emphasized the growing need for strategic discussions on the implementation of European federated computing at future large-scale research facilities. The workshop identified five priority areas for assessment. This report focuses on one of them, summarizing discussions on the needs and recommendations for integrating High-Performance Computing (HPC) centers with the High-Throughput Computing (HTC) systems used to manage and analyze data from large-scale experiments like the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG).

Despite a long history of using supercomputers, by the 1990s, the advent of commodity hardware and increased network capacities enabled high-performance distributed computing infrastructures. As a result, the JENA communities transitioned toward HTC centers, which better suited their workflows. However, over the last decade, the rapid growth of HPC facilities has made them a significant computing resource and triggered the interest from funding agencies on maximizing the utilization of these costly infrastructures.

¹ <https://agenda.infn.it/event/34738/timetable/>

The JENA communities acknowledge the potential and aspire to actively engage at a high level with the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU²). Looking ahead, there is an opportunity to influence the evolution and policies of HPC facilities to better align with the needs of the JENA sciences, with the twofold objective of expanding the available computing capacity for these communities and facilitating integration with existing data facilities.

This report has been written by the HPC Working Group (WG), a group of experts on HPC integration from the three JENA research areas. The members of the group are listed in the appendix. Monthly meetings were organised, between April and September 2024, with agendas available on the web³. The HPC WG benefits from synergies with other initiatives, including a working group initiated by CERN, WLCG and the LHC experiments on integrating High-Energy Physics (HEP) and HPC facilities, in which members of the JENA HPC WG participated. A strategy meeting⁴ with EuroHPC representatives took place in Ljubljana in September 2024. During that meeting, the outcomes of a similar HEP-HPC strategy⁵ meeting held in the U.S. earlier in the year were presented, aiming to leverage commonalities between both regions. Additionally, a joint Europe-America-Asia strategy meeting⁶ has been organized at CERN in January 2025. Another key initiative is the SPECTRUM⁷ EU-funded project, where members of the JENA WGs collaborated with SPECTRUM contributors — many of whom are involved in both initiatives. Together, they designed and distributed a survey to a “Community of Practice” that closely aligns with the JENA community. While the survey results are still being analyzed, they provide valuable insights into the current and future requirements of the JENA community. Finally, some of the discussions presented in this report were conducted jointly with the AI Infrastructure WG, one of the five strategic topics identified during the JENA Bologna workshop.

This report provides an overview of existing strategies across the JENA communities. It begins by outlining the scientific needs and the anticipated evolution of computing requirements and trends in three scientific areas. Next, it examines the development of HPC centers in Europe and beyond, focusing on initiatives particularly relevant to JENA. The report also summarizes key findings from the HEP-HPC strategy meetings and the SPECTRUM survey. It identifies critical technical and organizational areas that need development to effectively integrate HPC centers with experimental facilities. Finally, the WG presents its recommendations, addressing all three scientific communities.

Scientific needs

High Energy Physics

HEP experiments have played a major role in data-intensive scientific computing over the past decades, with unsurpassed requirements in software complexity, resource needs, and user base. While other communities are now making similar progress, HEP is not expected to experience a slowdown in increasing complexity, demands, or users. Upcoming experiments and other data-intensive scientific projects are projected to generate exabytes

² <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>

³ <https://indico.cern.ch/category/18034/>

⁴ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1436114/>

⁵ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1356688/>

⁶ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1466360/>

⁷ <https://www.spectrumproject.eu/>

of data per year—an order of magnitude increase from today—necessitating efficient collection, distribution, processing, and analysis.

To fully exploit the vast amounts of data that will be produced and maximize their physics potential, significant changes in processing techniques, technologies, and resources must be evaluated and adopted. HPC sites provide the largest computing resources available to scientific communities, making it imperative for HEP experiments to integrate these facilities. The goal is not only to manage the costs of standard WLCG centers but also to significantly expand the total resources available to the field, particularly in the challenging context of the high-luminosity LHC. This expansion directly enhances physics output by enabling, for example, more Monte Carlo simulations, leading to greater precision in measurements and the full realization of the LHC experiments' physics potential. The HEP distributed computing infrastructure remains essential for securing data repositories and providing a stable baseline compute contribution tailored to HEP needs. Leveraging HPC resources with GPU acceleration opens new frontiers for HEP by enabling the integration of AI algorithms and innovative data processing techniques, significantly boosting the efficiency and precision of large-scale data analysis.

A similar challenge exists for theoretical HEP and Nuclear Physics, particularly in computationally intensive domains such as lattice gauge theories. Successful HPC integration efforts have led to increasingly precise predictions for physics observables, benefiting the broader HEP and Nuclear Physics community. Among the five science domains categorized by EuroHPC, Computational Physics—encompassing Universe Sciences and Fundamental Constituents of Matter—receives the largest share of resources⁸. One of the drivers of this usage is the Lattice QCD community, which has developed mature parallel codes with excellent scaling and was an early adopter of accelerator hardware such as GPUs. The pursuit of ever-greater precision, driven by future experiments, necessitates scaling up the resources available to the lattice gauge theory community.

Integrating HPC facilities for HEP computing is a complex task. Numerous challenges must be addressed, as detailed in the following sections, including workflow and data management, resource provisioning and interoperability, and software integration.

Additionally, many funding agencies have a strategic interest in maximizing the use of HPC facilities for HEP and related fields, given their significant prior investments. HEP computing presents a valuable opportunity to enhance the computational efficiency of HPC systems by utilizing processing cycles left unused by large multi-node workflows.

Nuclear Physics

The in-depth study of strong interactions among quarks and gluons is becoming an increasingly prominent area in modern Nuclear Physics (NP). Upcoming experiments are expanding in both detector size and complexity, with large-scale NP experiments now rivaling HEP in technical demands. At the same time, data volumes and processing requirements are growing rapidly.

⁸ EuroHPC User Day 2024, https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/news-events/events/eurohpc-user-day-2024-2024-10-22_en

NP computing faces unique challenges. For example, studying hadron structure requires specialized Monte Carlo event generators to model spin-dependent effects, which are particularly computationally intensive. Another major challenge is measuring rare observables, which demands the rapid processing of large datasets with significant background noise. These challenges are further compounded by the increasing use of AI and advanced Machine Learning (ML) in experiment calibration and analysis, which are becoming integral to the field.

Beyond the technical challenges of NP experiments, their associated communities and collaborations face additional complexities due to their diverse sizes and unique computing needs. Unlike the more unified structure of HEP collaborations, NP communities are less monolithic, making the deployment and utilization of a shared, federated computing infrastructure more challenging.

A key example is the IT infrastructure supporting research at the upcoming Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research (FAIR)⁹. FAIR's computing model follows a centralized approach, leveraging its Green-IT Cube to enable efficient and cost-effective resource sharing across its many diverse communities for both online and offline computations. Additionally, FAIR adopts a federated distributed-computing model for less data-intensive tasks, such as Monte Carlo simulations and theoretical calculations, where access to and integration with large HPCs are essential.

The Nuclear Physics European Collaboration Committee (NuPECC) recently outlined its long-range plan (LRP) for 2024 and beyond¹⁰, emphasizing the critical role of computing infrastructures in advancing NP research. A key focus of the LRP is the federated approach to leveraging synergies among research projects across diverse collaborations and IT infrastructures.

Additionally, the LRP recommends facilitating and strengthening NP researchers' access to large HPC centers, with a particular emphasis on GPU clusters at various scales—ranging from centralized centers for large-scale projects to localized resources for individual research groups.

Astroparticle Physics

Astroparticle physics is a research field at the intersection of astronomy, particle physics, and cosmology. It uses the combined power of all cosmic messengers: cosmic rays, electromagnetic waves, neutrinos, and gravitational waves to advance our understanding of the Universe beyond the Standard Model of particle physics and the Big Bang Model of cosmology.

In 2016, the Astroparticle Physics European Consortium (APPEC) published its strategy for 2017–2026¹¹, outlining 21 recommendations addressing scientific, organizational, and societal challenges. One recommendation focused on the community's computing needs.

⁹ <https://fair-center.eu/>

¹⁰ https://www.nupecc.org/lrp2024/Documents/nupecc_lrp2024.pdf

¹¹

<https://www.appec.org/wp-content/uploads/Documents/Current-docs/APPEC-Strategy-Book-Proof-19-Feb-2018.pdf>, with a [mid-term update](#) in 2023

While these needs have been modest so far, upcoming large observatories dedicated to multi-messenger studies of the Universe will require significant computing resources for data analysis. To address this, APPEC urged all relevant experiments to rigorously assess their computing requirements, collaborate with other communities to share best practices, and ensure a balanced allocation of computing resources across Europe.

Next-generation gravitational wave detectors will achieve vastly improved sensitivity compared to current observatories, leading to the detection of more transient events that remain in-band for much longer. Detecting compact binary coalescences and performing the necessary parameter estimation follow-ups will significantly increase computing demands. Given the longer durations and higher number of signals, extracting information from these observations would be prohibitively expensive with current data analysis techniques. Additionally, more accurate signal models will be needed to fully exploit "louder" events, including multimessenger signatures beyond gravitational waves. This will require large-scale parameter space studies of Einstein equation solutions with matter. Beyond compact binaries, supernova simulations are also computationally intensive. To manage these demands, substantial research and development in software and analysis pipelines will be essential. However, even with optimized techniques, computing requirements will remain enormous. Streamlining access to HPC resources and integrating them effectively within distributed workflows will be critically important.

HPC centers landscape

HPC is part of the EU strategy to improve digital sovereignty, innovation, and scientific research capabilities. Several HPC initiatives have been launched by the European Commission (EC) in recent years. The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe¹², a landmark research infrastructure in the 2021 ESFRI roadmap and a predecessor to EuroHPC, aimed to enable high-impact scientific discovery and engineering R&D across all disciplines, enhance European competitiveness, and benefit society.

EuroHPC is a flagship initiative focused on developing a world-class supercomputing infrastructure in Europe, supporting research and innovation in HPC technologies, software, and applications, and establishing exascale and pre-exascale systems in Europe.

In addition, there are many other HPC centers or federations in European countries, such as CSCS in Switzerland and the NHR centers in Germany. Some of these are already used by JENA communities or could be of interest for future use.

EuroHPC JU

EuroHPC JU is a legal and funding entity created in 2018 that implements a model allowing the European Union and participating countries to coordinate their investments with the objective of deploying world-class supercomputers in Europe and supporting world-leading HPC.

Since 2021, EuroHPC JU has procured several HPC systems which are now operational and accessible to users across Europe. The largest ones are the following:

¹² <https://prace-ri.eu/>

- The LUMI pre-exascale system, operational since 2022.
- The Leonardo pre-exascale system, operational since 2023.
- The MareNostrum5 pre-exascale system, operational since 2024.
- Five petascale systems (MeluXina, Discoverer, Vega, Deucalion and Karolina) operational since 2021.

Two exascale systems are also in preparation:

- The Jupiter exascale system procurement was signed in 2023. The system is expected to be operational in 2025 and will be the first European system with a capacity reaching one exaflop.
- In 2023 the EuroHPC JU selected the Jules Verne consortium to host and operate in France the 2nd EuroHPC exascale supercomputer, Alice Recoque, expected to be operational around 2026.

The current HPC centres are characterised by a dual architecture based on both CPU- and GPU-equipped nodes. The next generation of HPC centres, optimized for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML workloads, will instead adopt a hybrid-architecture design largely based on GPUs due to their increased parallelism and cost efficiency. It is expected that infrastructures will become increasingly heterogeneous, given the availability of ARM-based systems, a foreseen increase of the RISC-V architecture and possibly of other kinds of accelerators.

Access Modes

Since EuroHPC infrastructures are co-funded by national funds and the EuroHPC JU, access to them is available through two channels.

National access has been successfully exercised in some infrastructures in large-scale projects by the JENA national communities.

Access to the EuroHPC JU infrastructure is provided free of charge to the European user community and is governed by the EuroHPC Access policy¹³. This policy defines different Access Modes, categorized based on several parameters, including the volume of resources offered, the complexity of the evaluation process, the type and maturity of targeted applications, and the periodicity of cut-off dates.

For Access Modes that allocate large proportions of system resources, a peer-review evaluation is required to rank applications. There are currently three such modes, each with an allocation duration of one year:

- Extreme Scale Access
- Regular Access
- Access for Artificial Intelligence and Data-Intensive Applications

Two additional Access Modes follow a simplified evaluation process to accelerate the review:

- Benchmark Access - Allocation of 3 months meant for users who want to collect performance data or test a method.

¹³ <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/document/download/30614065-6dd6-4206-8065-fc97948e5e2c>

- Development Access - Allocation of 6 to 12 months meant for projects focusing on code and algorithm development

Additionally, allocations can be granted through exceptional procedures as foreseen by Strategic Access and Emergency Access.

The European Union can propose strategic European initiatives for access to EuroHPC supercomputers directly to the EuroHPC JU Governing Board (GB), bypassing the peer-review process. However, these initiatives must still undergo a technical review and comply with the same reporting, data management, and project management requirements as other accepted applications. Up to 10% of the total access time on EuroHPC supercomputers can be allocated to strategic initiatives, with the specific share of resources determined by the GB.

Finally, Emergency Access can be granted to initiatives deemed essential by the Union for providing health-, climate-related, or other critical emergency support services for the public good.

Federated Supercomputers and AI Factories

In 2022, the EuroHPC JU launched a study to determine the best solution for interconnecting EuroHPC systems and providing related connectivity services. In 2023, a procurement for EuroHPC Federation Platform services was launched¹⁴. The federation of EuroHPC resources aims to deliver services for security and access control, data discovery, access and transfer, as well as carbon footprint assessment.

In 2023, the EuroHPC JU appointed the EuroHyPerCon¹⁵ consortium to conduct a study on hyper-connectivity of HPC resources. The study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the communication and connectivity needs between EuroHPC systems and other relevant European and national supercomputing and data infrastructures, the available technology and service providers, and the landscape of users. A tender¹⁶ was launched in December 2024 for the "Acquisition of Hyperconnectivity Services for HPC systems", with the objective to procure a Network-as-a-Service offering to deploy a hyper-connectivity network linking a large number of sites, several of them related to JENA scientific computing activities.

In July 2024, the EuroHPC JU expanded its scope to include the acquisition and operation of AI-optimized supercomputers. These so-called AI Factories¹⁷ aim to develop AI ecosystems centered around EuroHPC supercomputing facilities. A key feature of the AI Factories is their ability to interact with one another and collaborate with the broader AI and data ecosystems, including relevant European research infrastructures. Thirteen initiatives have been granted funding and will become operational starting in 2025.

¹⁴ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/eurohpc-federation-platform_en

¹⁵ <https://eurohypercon.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://ted.europa.eu/en/notice/-/detail/767038-2024>

¹⁷

https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/eurohpc-joint-undertaking-launches-ai-factories-calls-boost-european-leadership-trustworthy-ai-2024-09-10_en

International perspective

Many particle, nuclear, and astroparticle physics experiments and instruments are part of international collaborations extending beyond Europe. As a result, integrating HPC facilities requires careful coordination across global partnerships.

The Advanced Scientific Computing Research (ASCR) program¹⁸, an initiative of the U.S. Department of Energy's (DOE) Office of Science, is dedicated to advancing national capabilities in HPC, networking, and computational science. ASCR plays a leading role in global HPC efforts, providing researchers access to some of the world's fastest supercomputers.

Recognizing the growing consensus on the transformative potential of integrating computational, data management, and experimental research infrastructure, ASCR established the Integrated Research Infrastructure Task Force in February 2020. This Task Force serves as a platform to assess the opportunities, risks, and challenges associated with integrating major research infrastructures.

In 2023, the DOE Office of Science published a report¹⁹ highlighting the strategic importance of such integration and outlining the next steps toward realizing the vision for an Integrated Research Infrastructure (IRI).

The HEP-HPC European Strategy Group

A meeting in Ljubljana, Slovenia, in September 2024 brought together stakeholders from the HEP community, EuroHPC JU, PRACE, and CERN. The four LHC experiments presented their future computing needs and progress in integrating HPC resources. European HPC centers, including those operating LUMI, Vega, Deucalion, and Alps systems and the ones planning to host the future Jupiter and Jules Verne described their existing and planned facilities, expressing strong interest in collaborating with the HEP community.

Technical aspects were then examined, in various domains such as edge services and Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), workflow submission and handling, wide-area networking, software, and storage handling. Opportunities of common interest were identified.

The overarching goal is to secure Strategic Access to EuroHPC resources by engaging with the EC and the EuroHPC JU Governing Board, following a strong track record of successful Project Access applications.

The agreed approach is to adopt a gradual strategy, building on existing experience from national and local calls as well as Benchmark Access projects. This involves preparing common Development and Benchmark Access projects to foster trust and familiarity with EuroHPC systems. Once use cases are well established, researchers will be encouraged to submit Regular Access proposals. Additionally, the strategy should include active engagement with the EC and EuroHPC JU at all levels—ranging from presenting the HEP

¹⁸ <https://science.osti.gov/ascr>

¹⁹ <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1984466>

case to GB members and EC officials to actively participating in relevant user groups and HPC-related EU projects.

Joint SPECTRUM/JENA survey

SPECTRUM²⁰ is a project granted under the EC call HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-05, aimed at preparing a Computing Strategy for Data-Intensive Science Infrastructures in Europe for the HEP and Radio Astronomy domains. SPECTRUM brings together selected stakeholders from these two scientific domains, as well as experiments from e-Infrastructures (including HPCs, Clouds, and Quantum Computing). The former group provides guidance on directions and future needs, while the latter outlines expectations for new e-Infrastructures, focusing on technical and policy aspects.

SPECTRUM aims to: (i) Establish a Community of Practice (CoP) to gather and share insights on future directions and needs in data-intensive research, as well as on emerging e-Infrastructures. (ii) Develop a Strategic Research, Innovation, and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA) and a Technical Blueprint outlining agreed processing models and solutions, providing feedback on investment priorities to funding agencies and policymakers. The CoP aims to be as inclusive as possible. As a result, other communities were invited to participate, ensuring representation from all three JENA communities.

The JENA Computing WGs and the SPECTRUM project have prepared a shared survey to gather relevant insights from the scientific and infrastructure communities. The goal is to develop a consolidated view of current needs and future possibilities over the next 5–10 years. The survey covered several key areas, including Authentication and Authorization solutions, computing needs, data and network requirements, computing environments, software development, training and careers, use case definitions, and e-Infrastructures. Nearly 100 responses were submitted by scientific computing users, scientific initiative managers, e-Infrastructure managers, and research software engineers. All three JENA communities were represented, with a slight predominance of (theoretical + experimental) HEP. Given the diverse sources of responses—including facility managers, institutional representatives, and individual users—the interpretation of results may be systematically skewed. A more in-depth analysis is required to disentangle these different contributions and present a clearer, more coherent perspective²¹. Some preliminary findings are outlined in the Appendix for each area of concern to JENA Working Groups, providing an initial sense of the most relevant topics.

Current situation and challenges

Based on many years experience in integrating HPC facilities in HEP, the conclusions of the HEP-HPC strategy group and a preliminary analysis of the JENA-SPECTRUM survey, the following key areas have been identified as essential for enabling the effective integration of HPC centers and experimental facilities.

²⁰ <https://www.spectrumproject.eu/>

²¹ This will be a deliverable of the second half of the work plan of the SPECTRUM project.

Technical areas

Edge services should be exploited to address some typical HPC limitations, such as: the capability to receive external workloads (and bridge them to the internal batch system), and to insert (some parts of) the center storage into global data management systems; bridging external AAls with the specific users at a center; acting as proxies for services like software distribution (e.g. CVMFS) and direct data management; routing a part of internal traffic towards the general internet (via NAT and routing mechanism).

Federated Access, AAI: The use of “special users”, or possibly service accounts, combined with edge services, would streamline the management of complex tasks such as executing generic user jobs and enabling data management systems to write to the filesystem.

Workflow management: JENA workflows, particularly those in experimental HEP, differ significantly from typical HPC workflows due to their complex codebases, numerous dependencies, late binding, and the need to access external services that may not be known before runtime. Adapting these workflows for HPC is a challenging task that will require efforts across multiple areas, as the solutions developed so far are simply not scalable, efficient, or sustainable. Comprehensive code reengineering and the development of new workflow orchestration strategies will be essential to overcome these limitations and create truly viable solutions for the long term.

Global networking: Wide-Area Network (WAN) is a crucial asset. This is often implicitly assumed due to the excellent availability and reliability of the backbone provided by NRENs, which interconnect most HTC centers through private networks such as LHCOPN and LHCONE²². The successful integration of HPC centers depends on their ability to connect to this backbone at high bandwidth, in an IPv6-compliant manner, while also extending logical layers like DMZs and trusted networks.

Data management: Efficient and reliable delivery of science data to and from HPC centers requires close integration with the frameworks already used by HEP experiments, built on open and widely adopted standards. The current reliance on custom edge services as a workaround is neither sustainable nor maintainable for the HL-LHC era. Greater effort is needed to develop seamless data transfer capabilities between existing JENA HTC data infrastructures and HPC persistent storage systems.

Software deployment: The use of CVMFS²³ is expanding across various scientific domains, making it the preferred solution for HPC centers. Additionally, containers can serve as an alternative for encapsulating experiment software, though they are generally less practical.

Programming models: The gap between current JENA domain workflows and accelerated hardware in HPC centers should be addressed through high-level frameworks such as Kokkos, Alpaka, SYCL, and C++ extensions. HPC sites consider this an application-level issue. Providing support for training, testing, and optimization would be highly beneficial.

²² <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/664/5/052025>

²³ <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

Organizational areas

Resource access: The lack of long-term HPC resource allocations impacts the reliability of critical workflows. A potential solution could involve collaboration with funding agencies and HPC providers to develop more stable allocation models. Some national agreements provide guaranteed strategic allocations, but the frequent call mechanism for proposal submissions does not align with the multi-annual timescale of research projects.

Training and retaining talent: Attracting and retaining young software developers skilled in accelerator programming and portable software design is a major challenge in today's competitive market. These developers are essential for the sustainable improvement of scientific software. Addressing this issue requires a focused effort to ensure attractive career paths within our institutions.

Conclusions and recommendations

Distributed computing systems have become essential for large physics experiments, effectively handling massive data volumes and enabling collaboration among geographically distributed researchers. This approach has been further strengthened by interdisciplinary collaboration, with researchers across experimental fields co-developing and sharing tools to improve distributed computing infrastructures for data analysis. At the same time, there is a trend by which computing resources in HPC centers have grown considerably over the past few years. This trend likely stems from a combination of geopolitical, strategic, technical and other factors. This substantial investment implies that funding agencies expect maximum usage across multiple scientific fields to make it effective. This can be seen as an opportunity for scientific communities to leverage the advantages of large-scale facilities, motivating them to adapt and integrate HPC systems with their existing distributed data infrastructure, with potential benefits in the sustainability of the computing infrastructure.

HPC sites generally feature modern architectures with high performance-to-power efficiency and state-of-the-art cooling systems. An integrated ecosystem—encompassing experiments, data facilities, HTC, and HPC centers—holds significant potential to accelerate scientific discovery and enhance international competitiveness. However, several key challenges must be addressed to fully unlock this potential. Some of these challenges are outlined below.

To effectively drive its core scientific program, JENA requires dedicated computing and data infrastructure. While integrating with national, European, and international HPC infrastructures is beneficial, it is critical to recognize that JENA's research activities, often driven by communities with diverse computing needs, rely heavily on flexible, scalable HTC resources. Furthermore, the unique datasets produced by JENA are an invaluable asset, requiring dedicated, non-outsourced infrastructure. There is a real risk that the priorities of EuroHPC centers may not fully align with the specific, research-driven needs of JENA communities. Therefore, sustained investment in dedicated JENA computing and data infrastructure, coupled with regional and national programs specifically tailored to these communities' scientific requirements, is essential for JENA's long-term success and scientific advancement.

The software and computing landscape across the three JENA communities is inherently diverse. To develop a coherent roadmap for efficiently utilizing large HPC systems, a

coordinated approach is needed towards EuroHPC from these communities. This effort aims to establish a roadmap for addressing technical gaps and to provide a consistent picture of global needs in preparation for a Strategic Access application. The ultimate goal is to be recognized as a strategic activity, enabling multi-year allocations of compute and storage at HPC facilities allowing these resources to be integrated into the long-term capacity planning of research groups and collaborations.

Effectively integrating HPC resources into research workflows will require substantial efforts in software development, including optimizing scientific codes for emerging architectures, and developing workflow and data orchestration software. Securing adequate funding for these activities and investing in flexible software design will be crucial. Long-term HPC access can expand available resources, enhancing the physics potential of multi-billion-euro instruments or freeing up funds for essential software development. A crucial factor for success is establishing a strategy for training and retaining talent in scientific software development, a topic specifically studied by one of the five WGs formed during the JENA Bologna workshop.

With the unroll of initiatives like the Federation Platform and the AI Factories, EuroHPC JU systems are evolving towards a more interconnected and data-centric architecture. This evolution presents an opportunity to leverage the valuable experience gained from successful programs such as the WLCG in distributed computing systems for data analysis. Communication and collaboration mechanisms should be identified, both at the technical and political level, in order to ensure that the future global scientific computing landscape builds on the strengths of current systems. Specifically, it is crucial to create processes that ensure the needs of large scientific communities, such as those represented by JENA, are considered during the design, procurement and operation of HPC systems at the regional, national, European and international levels. An important aspect in this context is the necessity for standardized and mutually agreed-upon policies and interfaces across HPC centers to facilitate access to these infrastructures, covering areas such as AAI, data transfers, networking, edge services, container support, and more.

Significant uncertainties remain in predicting the GPU needs of scientific collaborations. Tracking the evolution of these needs and assessing their impact on computing models and distributed computing infrastructure will be essential. This requires establishing mechanisms for regular assessment, using agreed-upon metrics to monitor GPU usage and update resource estimations. The findings from these assessments should be incorporated into the roadmap for integrating HPC resources.

In conclusion, integrating HPC infrastructures within distributed computing systems offers a transformative opportunity to accelerate scientific discovery and enhance global competitiveness. However, fully realizing this potential requires a coordinated, interdisciplinary effort to overcome key challenges, including software optimization, resource federation, strategic access to computing resources, and talent development. By building on the experiences of successful programs like WLCG and embracing emerging initiatives such as the AI Factories and the Federation Platform, the scientific community can build a more interconnected, data-centric ecosystem. Ongoing efforts to assess and adapt to evolving needs—particularly regarding GPU usage—will be critical to ensuring the long-term success of these integrated systems. Ultimately, harmonizing technical, financial, and organizational strategies will be essential to advancing both distributed and HPC computing, enabling

future scientific breakthroughs. While this report primarily focuses on EuroHPC, its findings and recommendations are equally relevant to other HPC initiatives, including PRACE, national HPC centers, and non-European facilities.

Appendix: Preliminary finding of the JENA/SPECTRUM survey, relevant to this working group

Feedback from users and research projects

1. **AAI** is a central piece in today's computing. There are several solutions that allow for a precise auditing of activities in case of malicious activities. Only a small fraction of users still use username/password; Users nevertheless prefer to be shielded by AAI methods as much as possible, often seeing them as unfriendly. While there is not a common default solution, most of them are interoperable by design, with two/multi factor authentication getting traction.
2. Regarding **processing needs**, there is no clear predominance between workflow types (simulation, data processing, theory calculations, ML/AI training/inference, high-level data analysis), while "old fashioned" batch and shell accesses are still the majority. Applications running on single-core or multi-core are preferred over multi-node²⁴. Total resource needs range from 200,000 to five billions core hours per year. Most applications are not ready today for GPU utilization.
3. The preferred **facilities** are Grid facilities and HPC centers; in general, there is not an overwhelming majority for any category. When using resources that are not directly owned, an important factor is the stability of the allocation: experiments are multi-annual initiatives, and need to have guaranteed access to resources for a reasonable time period.
4. In most cases, as expected in data-intensive sciences with distributed data silos, access to **external services** is needed. This is a source of concern for using HPC facilities, due to their somewhat strict access and networking policies.
 - a. **Accessing (large) datasets** in particular is a complex operation, with approaches ranging from local data reading to remote streaming. The former is preferred, where data is moved to the processing center either via managed transfers or as a first step in data processing on the compute nodes.
 - b. **Resource discovery** in a distributed computing environment is not a trivial task. Both push (a managed catalogue of resources to submit to) and pull (auto-registration) modes are used, in almost perfect balance among the answers.
5. **Data management** is a difficult task in large, data-intensive initiatives. Depending on the size, datasets up to multiple exabytes must be distributed among tens if not hundreds of storage centers, by moving files on regional, continental and intercontinental routes. Data can be anything between files, DB tables, images, and such.
 - a. The **average bandwidth** of data ingestion into the distributed computing system is very relevant. In most of the cases (> 50%), exceeding 1 GB/s and larger than 1 TB/s in 7% of the cases. **Wide-Area Network** is therefore a crucial asset. This is somewhat implicitly assumed, given the excellent availability and reliability of the backbone provided by the NRENs.
 - b. **Data management solutions**, on the initiatives' side, are essential with such large data samples. Most initiatives use open-source tools for that, but

²⁴ A relevant exception being the simulation of lattice gauge field theories.

in-house and commercial solutions are not excluded. FTS is emerging as the data mover work-horse; initiatives with smaller data movement needs are working without FTS.

- c. Data transfers between two storage systems must use **protocols** understood by them; It is important that the data transfer tool allows for the largest variety of protocols, to match those supported by the initiatives in their storage sites. There is quite a flat preference between Grid, Cloud protocols, with a minority using old protocols like bare FTP.
 - d. Each domain has usually converged to a small number of shared **data format** solutions. Data is typically organised on files or DB tables, with the most common file sizes being over 1 GB, not to clog transfer systems. The objects the researchers are interested in are in most cases files, but DB records are not absent. The number of objects to be managed, tracked and transferred can be very high, exceeding 1 billion in about one third of the initiatives.
 - e. There is a consistent transition towards **F.A.I.R. data**. This does not necessarily mean open data: the most used definition is “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Some initiatives declare their data as simply “open”; in all other cases, embargoes are used to limit initial access, or the data is simply closed. In both cases, a mechanism ensuring only the authorized persons can access the data is needed.
 - f. Coming to **data interpretation**, the situation varies between self-describing data (for example text files) and simple byte streams which cannot be interpreted without a schema, external data, or similar.
6. **Expected compute environment:** The execution of scientific workflows on a system not explicitly managed to support them is at times not compatible with a given center hardware, software, or even political configurations, resulting in a series of technical details that can make the process infinitely painful, if not impossible.
- a. There are no big requirements on the **operating system**, provided it is a modern 64-bit Linux. The preferred GPUs are the NVidia ones; some initiatives are able to address at least other vendors (Intel, AMD). The total fraction of the workflows that can indeed be offloaded to GPUs is well below 50%.
 - b. The JENA domains are data-intensive, hence it is no big surprise that computing elements need to access **external resources**. In the vast majority of cases, the workflows seem not to request root access.
 - c. **Software installation**, especially when in the presence of large software stacks, is problematic and not always possible from the user point of view. External solutions vary from “an email to the sysadmins” to the use of package managers, to the use of pre-cooked sw deployment like for CVMFS, to the use of virtualized systems. Quite surprisingly, most initiatives declare they do not use edge services.

Feedback from E-infrastructures managers

1. The most commonly **offered resources** are CPU and GPU centers, either classified as HTC (Grid facilities and computing farms) or HPCs (supercomputers). Centers can either be managed directly or be part of a larger infrastructure, like WLCG or EuroHPC JU, or EGI.

2. **Access to resources** can be offered in various manners: as response to bids, by funding the center, using pay-per-use; the most used method is local / national / institutional access. In about 50% of cases, deploying community services on the computing center is not allowed. The preferred option to allocate resources to the users, using some form of resource sharing, is still through batch systems. Allocations can have different lengths: 12 months or less (from typical EU grants) to very long term (for example when a community directly funded a center).
3. Most centers offer x86_64 architectures, with 2-4 GB RAM per core and a few tens of GB scratch disk; the latest hardware procured included at least one GPU, more frequently 4 or more.
4. Fast network connections (10-100 Gbps) between storage nodes, and fast (>100 Gbps) WAN connections are generally available. Incoming and outgoing network connections from/to onsite nodes are generally allowed, while it is more varied for outside locations.
5. "Industry standard" (for example WebDAV, S3, ..) and "domain specific" (XrootD, ...) storage transfer protocols offered at user jobs for connection are available at a subset of the centers. The existence of a proper "user to center" matched transfer protocol still needs to be checked case by case.
6. Solutions for software distribution like CVMFS are typical in HTC centers (for example those in WLCG), while they are reportedly not a supported solution in HPC centers. There is however a general tendency towards virtualization, which (also) helps in software distribution.
7. Authentication and authorization are mostly federated via trust networks.

Appendix: Members of the HPC Working Group

Chairs:

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